

**AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
STRESS DETECTION IN IT PROFESSIONAL BY IMAGE
PROCESSING AND MACHINE LEARNING
BY
KAMAL ACHARYA
(Tribhuvan University)**

Date: 2025/07/09

CONTENTS

TOPIC	PAGENO
ABSTRACT	I
LIST OF FIGURES	II
1. INTRODUCTION	1
Introduction& Objectives	1
Different Types of Rice Plant Diseases	2
ProjectObjectives	3
Purpose oftheProject	4
Existing system& Disadvantages	4
Proposed systemwith Features	5
2. LITERATURESURVEY	6
3. SOFTWARE REQUIREMENT ANALYSIS	8
ProblemSpecification	8
Modules andtheirFunctionalities	8
FunctionalRequirements	12
Non-Functional Requirements	12
FeasibilityStudy	12
4. SOFTWARE &HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS	14
Softwarerequirements	14
Hardwarerequirements	14
5. SOFTWAREDESIGN	15
SystemArchitecture	15
DataflowDiagrams	17
E-RDiagrams	24
UMLDiagrams	25

6. CODING AND IMPLEMENTATION	35
Sourcecode	35
Implementation	61
ProjectStructure	54
InAnaconda Prompt	56
7. SYSTEM TESTING	59
Types ofSystem Testing	59
TestingStrategies	59
8. OUTPUT SCREENS	61
9. CONCLUSION	63
10. FUTURE ENHANCEMENTS	64
11. REFERENCES	65

ABSTRACT

The main motive of our project is to detect stress in the IT professionals using vivid Machine learning and Image processing techniques. Our system is an upgraded version of the old stress detection systems which excluded the live detection and the personal counseling but this system comprises of live detection and periodic analysis of employees and detecting physical as well as mental stress levels in his/her by providing them with proper remedies for managing stress by providing survey form periodically. Our system mainly focuses on managing stress and making the working environment healthy and spontaneous for the employees and to get the best out of them during working hours.

LIST OF FIGURES

S.NO	FIGURE NO	DESCRIPTION	PAGENO
1	1.1.1.1	Brownspot	2
2	1.1.1.2	Leaf Blast	3
3	1.1.1.3	Hispa	3
6	5.1	System Architecture	15
7	5.2	Data flow diagram	18
8	5.3	E-R diagram	25
9	5.4.1	Sequence diagram	26
10	5.4.2	Usecase diagram	27
11	5.4.3	Activity diagram	28
12	6.2.1	Install tensorflow	53
13	6.2.2	Install keras	54
14	6.2.3	Install opencv	54
15	6.2.4	Install pillow	54
16	6.2.1.1	Annotations Structure	55
17	6.2.1.2	Tags	56
18	6.2.1.3	Draw the bounding boxes	56
19	6.2.2.1	Convert to yolo format	57
20	6.2.2.2	Download and convert yolo pre trained	57
21	6.2.2.3	Training yolov3	58
22	8.1	Testing the images	61
23	8.2	Display output	61

24	8.3	BrownSpot	62
25	8.4	Hispa	62
26	8.5	Leaf Blast	62
27	8.6	Healthy	62

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction & Objectives

Stress management systems play a significant role to detect the stress levels which disrupts our socio economic lifestyle. As World Health Organization (WHO) says, Stress is a mental health problem affecting the life of one in four citizens. Human stress leads to mental as well as socio-fiscal problems, lack of clarity in work, poor working relationship, depression and finally commitment of suicide in severe cases. This demands counseling to be provided for the stressed individuals cope up against stress. Stress avoidance is impossible but preventive actions helps to overcome the stress. Currently, only medical and physiological experts can determine whether one is under depressed state (stressed) or not. One of the traditional method to detect stress is based on questionnaire. This method completely depends on the answers given by the individuals, people will be tremulous to say whether they are stressed or normal. Automatic detection of stress minimizes the risk of health issues and improves the welfare of the society. This paves the way for the necessity of a scientific tool, which uses physiological signals thereby automating the detection of stress levels in individuals. Stress detection is discussed in various literatures as it is a significant societal contribution that enhances the lifestyle of individuals. Ghaderiet al. analysed stress using Respiration, Heart rate (HR), facial electromyography (EMG), Galvanic skin response (GSR) foot and GSR hand data with a conclusion that, features pertaining to respiration process are substantial in stress detection. Maria Viqueira et al. describes mental stress prediction using a standalone stress sensing hardware by interfacing GSR as the only physiological sensor. David Liu et al. proposed a research to predict stress levels solely from Electrocardiogram (ECG). Multimodal sensor efficacy to detect stress of working people is experimentally discussed in. This employs the sensor data from sensors such as pressure distribution, HR, Blood Volume Pulse (BVP) and Electro dermal activity (EDA). An eye tracker sensor is also used which systematically analyses the eye movements with the stressors like Stroop word test and information related to pickup tasks. The authors of performed perceived stress detection by a set of non-invasive sensors which collects the physiological signals such as ECG, GSR, Electroencephalography (EEG), EMG, and Saturation of peripheral oxygen (SpO₂). Continuous stress levels are estimated using the physiological sensor data such as GSR, EMG, HR, Respiration in. The stress

detection is carried out effectively using Skin conductance level (SCL), HR, Facial EMG sensors by creating ICT related Stressors. Automated stress detection is made possible by several pattern recognition algorithms. Every sensor data is compared with a stress index which is a threshold value used for detecting the stress level. The authors of collected data from 16 individuals under four stressor conditions which were tested with Bayesian Network, J48 algorithm and Sequential Minimal Optimization (SMO) algorithm for predicting stress. Statistical features of heart rate, GSR, frequency domain features of heart rate and its variability (HRV), and the power spectral components of ECG were used to govern the stress levels. Various features are extracted from the commonly used physiological signals such as ECG, EMG, GSR, BVP etc., measured using appropriate sensors and selected features are grouped into clusters for further detection of anxiety levels . In, it is concluded that smaller clusters result in better balance in stress detection using the selected General Regression Neural Network (GRNN) model. This results in the fact that different combinations of the extracted features from the sensor signals provide better solutions to predict the continuous anxiety level. Frequency domain features like LF power (low frequency power from 0.04 Hz to 0.15Hz), HF power (High frequency power from 0.15Hz to 0.4 Hz) , LF/HF (ratio of LF to the HF) and time domain features like Mean , Median, standard deviation of heart signal are considered for continuous real time stress detection in . Classification using decision tree such as PLDA is performed using two stressors namely pickup task and stroop based word test wherein the authors concluded that the stressor based classification proves unsatisfactory. In 2016, Gjoreski et al. created laboratory based stress detection classifiers from ECG signal and HRV features. Features of ECG are analysed using GRNN model to measure the stress level. Heart rate variability (HRV) features and RR (cycle length variability interval length between two successive Rs) interval features are used to classify the stress level. It is noticed that Support Vector Machine (SVM) was used as the classification algorithm predominantly due to its generalization ability and sound mathematical background Various kernels were used to develop models using SVM and it is concluded in that a linear SVM on both ECG frequency features and HRV features performed best, outperforming other model choices.

Nowadays as IT industries are setting a new peek in the market by bringing new technologies and products in the market. In this study, the stress levels in employees are also noticed to raise the bar high. Though there are many organizations who provide mental health related schemes for their employees but the issue is far from control. In this paper

we try to go in the depth of this problem by trying to detect the stress patterns in the working employee in the companies we would like to apply image processing and machine learning techniques to analyze stress patterns and to narrow down the factors that strongly determine the stress levels. Machine Learning algorithms like KNN classifiers are applied to classify stress. Image Processing is used at the initial stage for detection, the employee's image is clicked by the camera which serves as input. In order to get an enhanced image or to extract some useful information from it image processing is used by converting image into digital form and performing some operations on it. By taking input as an image from video frames and output may be image or characteristics associated with that image. Image processing basically includes the following three steps:

- Importing the image via image acquisition tools.
- Analyzing and manipulating the image.
- Output in which result is altered image or report that is based on image analysis.

System gets the ability to automatically learn and improve from self-experiences without being explicitly programmed using Machine learning which is an application of artificial intelligence (AI). Computer programs are developed by Machine Learning that can access data and use it to learn for themselves. Explicit programming to perform the task based on predictions or decisions builds a mathematical model based on "training data" by using Machine Learning. The extraction of hidden data, association of image data and additional pattern which are unclearly visible in image is done using Image Mining. It's an interrelated field that involves, Image Processing, Data Mining, Machine Learning and Datasets. According to conservative estimates in medical books, 50- 80% of all physical diseases are caused by stress. Stress is believed to be the principal cause in cardiovascular diseases. Stress can place one at higher risk for diabetes, ulcers, asthma, migraine headaches, skin disorders, epilepsy, and sexual dysfunction. Each of these diseases, and host of others, is psychosomatic (i.e., either caused or exaggerated by mental conditions such as stress) in nature. Stress has three prong effects:

- Subjective effects of stress include feelings of guilt, shame, anxiety, aggression or frustration. Individuals also feel tired, tense, nervous, irritable, moody, or lonely.
- Visible changes in a person's behavior are represented by Behavioral effects of stress. Effects of behavioral stress are seen such as increased accidents, use of drugs or alcohol, laughter out of context, outlandish or argumentative behavior, very excitable moods, and/or

eating or drinking to excess.

□ Diminishing mental ability, impaired judgment, rash decisions, forgetfulness and/or hypersensitivity to criticism are some of the effects of Cognitive stress

Project Objectives

By the end of this project you'll understand

1. To predict stress in a person by the symptoms calculated by monitoring.
2. To analyze the stress levels in the employee.
3. To provide solutions and remedies for the person to recover his/her stress

Purpose of the Project

Nowadays as IT industries are setting a new peek in the market by bringing new technologies and products in the market. In this study, the stress levels in employees are also noticed to raise the bar high. Stress can place one at higher risk for diabetes, ulcers, asthma, migraine headaches, skin disorders, epilepsy, and sexual dysfunction. In this project we try to go in the depth of this problem by trying to detect the stress patterns in the working employee in the companies we would like to apply image processing and machine learning techniques to analyze stress patterns and to narrow down the factors that strongly determine the stress levels. Machine Learning algorithms like KNN classifiers are applied to classify stress. Image Processing is used at the initial stage for detection, the employee's image is clicked by the camera which serves as input. In order to get an enhanced image or to extract some useful information from it image processing is used by converting image into digital form and performing some operations on it. By taking input as an image from video frames and output may be image or characteristics associated with that image.

Existing System with Disadvantages

In the existing system work on stress detection is based on the digital signal processing, taking into consideration Galvanic skin response, blood volume, pupil dilation and skin temperature. And the other work on this issue is based on several physiological signals and visual features (eye closure, head movement) to monitor the stress in a person while he is working. However these measurements are intrusive and are less comfortable in real application. Every sensor data is compared with a stress index which is a threshold value used for detecting the stress level.

Disadvantages

1. Physiological signals used for analysis are often pigeonholed by a Non-stationary time performance.
2. The extracted features explicitly gives the stress index of the physiological signals. The ECG signal is directly assessed by using commonly used peak j48 algorithm
3. Different people may behave or express differently under stress and it is hard to find a universal pattern to define the stress emotion.

Proposed System withFeatures

The proposed System Machine Learning algorithms like KNN classifiers are applied to classify stress. Image Processing is used at the initial stage for detection, the employee's image is given by the browser which serves as input. In order to get an enhanced image or to extract some useful information from it image processing is used by converting image into digital form and performing some operations on it. By taking input as an image and output may be image or characteristics associated with that images. The emotion are displayed on the rounder box. The stress level indicating by Angry, Disgusted, Fearful, Sad.

Advantages

1. By taking input as an image and output may be image or characteristics associated with that images.
2. We will capture images of the employee based on the regular intervals and then the tradition survey forms will be given to the employees
3. The emotions are displayed on the rounder box. The stress level indicating by Angry, Disgusted, Fearful, Sad.

INPUT AND OUTPUT DESIGN

INPUT DESIGN

The input design is the link between the information system and the user. It comprises the developing specification and procedures for data preparation and those steps are necessary to put transaction data in to a usable form for processing can be achieved by inspecting the computer to read data from a written or printed document or it can occur by having people keying the data directly into the system. The design of input focuses on controlling the amount of input required, controlling the errors, avoiding delay, avoiding extra steps and keeping the process simple. The input is designed in such a way so that it provides security and ease of use with retaining the privacy. Input Design considered the following things:

- What data should be given as input?
- How the data should be arranged or coded?
- The dialog to guide the operating personnel in providing input.
- Methods for preparing input validations and steps to follow when error occur.

OBJECTIVES

1. Input Design is the process of converting a user-oriented description of the input into a computer-based system. This design is important to avoid errors in the data input process and show the correct direction to the management for getting correct information from the computerized system.
2. It is achieved by creating user-friendly screens for the data entry to handle large volume of data. The goal of designing input is to make data entry easier and to be free from errors. The data entry screen is designed in such a way that all the data manipulates can be performed. It also provides record viewing facilities.

3. When the data is entered it will check for its validity. Data can be entered with the help of screens. Appropriate messages are provided as when needed so that the user will not be in maize of instant. Thus the objective of input design is to create an input layout that is easy to follow

OUTPUT DESIGN

A quality output is one, which meets the requirements of the end user and presents the information clearly. In any system results of processing are communicated to the users and to other system through outputs. In output design it is determined how the information is to be displaced for immediate need and also the hard copy output. It is the most important and direct source information to the user. Efficient and intelligent output design improves the system's relationship to help user decision-making.

1. Designing computer output should proceed in an organized, well thought out manner; the right output must be developed while ensuring that each output element is designed so that people will find the system can use easily and effectively. When analysis design computer output, they should Identify the specific output that is needed to meet the requirements.
2. Select methods for presenting information.
3. Create document, report, or other formats that contain information produced by the system.

The output form of an information system should accomplish one or more of the following objectives.

- Convey information about past activities, current status or projections of the Future.
- Signal important events, opportunities, problems, or warnings.
- Trigger an action.
- Confirm an action.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

1. Stress and anxiety detection using facial cues from videos

AUTHORS:G. Giannakakis, D. Manousos, F. Chiarugi

This study develops a framework for the detection and analysis of stress/anxiety emotional states through video-recorded facial cues. A thorough experimental protocol was established to induce systematic variability in affective states (neutral, relaxed and stressed/anxious) through a variety of external and internal stressors. The analysis was focused mainly on non-voluntary and semi-voluntary facial cues in order to estimate the emotion representation more objectively. Features under investigation included eye-related events, mouth activity, head motion parameters and heart rate estimated through camera-based photo plethysmography. A feature selection procedure was employed to select the most robust features followed by classification schemes discriminating between stress/anxiety and neutral states with reference to a relaxed state in each experimental phase. In addition, a ranking transformation was proposed utilizing self reports in order to investigate the correlation of facial parameters with a participant perceived amount of stress/anxiety. The results indicated that, specific facial cues, derived from eye activity, mouth activity, head movements and camera based heart activity achieve good accuracy and are suitable as discriminative indicators of stress and anxiety.

2. Detection of Stress Using Image Processing and Machine Learning Techniques

AUTHORS: Nisha Raichur, Nidhi Lonakadi, Priyanka Mural

Stress is a part of life it is an unpleasant state of emotional arousal that people experience in situations like working for long hours in front of computer. Computers have become a way of life, much life is spent on the computers and hence we are therefore more affected by the ups and downs that they cause us. One cannot just completely avoid their work on computers but one can at least control his/her usage when being alarmed about him being stressed at certain point of time. Monitoring the emotional status of a person who is working in front of a computer for longer duration is crucial for the safety of a person. In this work a real-time non-intrusive videos are captured, which detects the emotional status of a person by analysing the facial expression. We detect an individual emotion in each video frame and the decision on the stress level is made in sequential hours of the video captured. We employ a technique that allows us to train a model and

analyze differences in predicting the features. Theano is a python framework which aims at improving both the execution time and development time of the linear regression model which is used here as a deep learning algorithm. The experimental results show that the developed system is well on data with the generic model of all ages.

3. Machine Learning Techniques for Stress Prediction in Working Employees

AUTHORS:U. S. Reddy, A. V. Thota and A. Dharun

Stress disorders are a common issue among working IT professionals in the industry today. With changing lifestyle and work cultures, there is an increase in the risk of stress among the employees. Though many industries and corporates provide mental health related schemes and try to ease the workplace atmosphere, the issue is far from control. In this paper, we would like to apply machine learning techniques to analyze stress patterns in working adults and to narrow down the factors that strongly determine the stress levels. Towards this, data from the OSMI mental health survey 2017 responses of working professionals within the tech-industry was considered. Various Machine Learning techniques were applied to train our model after due data cleaning and preprocessing. The accuracy of the above models was obtained and studied comparatively. Boosting had the highest accuracy among the models implemented. By using Decision Trees, prominent features that influence stress were identified as gender, family history and availability of health benefits in the workplace. With these results, industries can now narrow down their approach to reduce stress and create a much comfortable workplace for their employees.

4. Classification of acute stress using linear and non-linear heart rate variability analysis derived from sternal ECG

AUTHORS :Tanev, G., Saadi, D.B., Hoppe, K., Sorensen, H.B

Chronic stress detection is an important factor in predicting and reducing the risk of cardiovascular disease. This work is a pilot study with a focus on developing a method for detecting short-term psychophysiological changes through heart rate variability (HRV) features. The purpose of this pilot study is to establish and to gain insight on a set of features that could be used to detect psychophysiological changes that occur during chronic stress. This study elicited four different types of arousal by images, sounds, mental tasks and rest, and classified them using linear and non-linear HRV features from electrocardiograms (ECG) acquired by the wireless wearable ePatch® recorder. The highest recognition rates were acquired for the neutral stage (90%), the

acute stress stage (80%) and the baseline stage (80%) by sample entropy, detrended fluctuation analysis and normalized high frequency features. Standardizing non-linear HRV features for each subject was found to be an important factor for the improvement of the classification results.

5. HealthyOffice: Mood recognition at work using smartphones and wearable sensors

AUTHORS: Zenonos, A., Khan, A., Kalogridis, G., Vatsikas, S., Lewis, T., Sooriyabandara

Stress, anxiety and depression in the workplace are detrimental to human health and productivity with significant financial implications. Recent research in this area has focused on the use of sensor technologies, including smartphones and wearables embedded with physiological and movement sensors. In this work, we explore the possibility of using such devices for mood recognition, focusing on work environments. We propose a novel mood recognition framework that is able to identify five intensity levels for eight different types of moods every two hours. We further present a smartphone app ('HealthyOffice'), designed to facilitate self-reporting in a structured manner and provide our model with the ground truth. We evaluate our system in a small-scale user study where wearable sensing data is collected in an office environment. Our experiments exhibit promising results allowing us to reliably recognize various classes of perceived moods.

3. SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS ANALYSIS

Problem Specification

According to conservative estimates in medical books, 50- 80% of all physical diseases are caused by stress. Stress is believed to be the principal cause in cardiovascular diseases. Stress can place one at higher risk for diabetes, ulcers, asthma, migraine headaches, skin disorders, epilepsy, and sexual dysfunction. So in this project we are trying to detect the stress patterns in the working employee in the companies we would like to apply image processing and machine learning techniques to analyze stress patterns and to narrow down the factors that strongly determine the stress levels.

Modules and Their Functionalities

1. USER:

The User can register the first. While registering he required a valid user email and mobile for further communications. Once the user register then admin can activate the customer. Once admin activated the customer then user can login into our system. First user has to give the input as image to the system. The python library will extract the features and appropriate emotion of the image. If given image contain more than one faces also possible to detect. The stress level we are going to indicate by facial expression like sad, angry etc.. The image processing completed the we are going to start the live stream. In the live stream also we can get the facial expression more that one persons also. Compare to tensorflow live stream the tesnorflow live stream will fast and better results. Once done the we are loading the dataset to perform the knn classification accuracy precession scores.

2. Admin:

Admin can login with his credentials. Once he login he can activate the users. The activated user only login in our applications. The admin can set the training and testing data for the project dynamically to the code. The admin can view all users detected results in hid frame. By click in gan hyperlink in the screen he can detect the emotions of the images. The admin can also view the knn classification detected results. The dataset in the excel format. By authorized persons we can increase the dataset size according the imaginary values.

3. DATA PREPROCESS:

Dataset contains grid view of already stored dataset consisting numerous properties, by Property Extraction newly designed dataset appears which contains only numerical input variables as a result of Principal Component Analysis feature selection transforming to 6 principal components which are Condition (No stress, Time pressure, Interruption), Stress, Physical Demand, Performance and Frustration.

4. MACHINE LEARNING:

K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN) is used for classification as well as regression analysis. It is a supervised learning algorithm which is used for predicting if a person needs treatment or not. KNN classifies the dependent variable based on how similar it is; independent variables are to a similar instance from the already known data. the Knn Classification can be called as a statistical model that uses a binary dependent variable. In classification analysis, KNN is estimating the parameters of a KNN model. Mathematically, a binary KNN model has a dependent variable with two possible value, which is represented by an indicator variable, where the two values are labeled "0" and "1".

a. Functional Requirements

It provides the users a clear statement of the functions required for the system in order to solve the project information problem it contain a complete set of requirements for the applications.

A requirement is condition that the application must meet for the customer to find the application satisfactory. A requirement has the following characteristics

1. It provides a benefit to the origination.
2. It describes the capabilities the application must provide in business terms.
3. It does not describe how the application provides that capability.
4. It is stated in unambiguous words. Its meaning is clear and understandable.
5. It is verifiable.

b. Non Functional Requirements

Stress non-functional requirements, like diseases, the architects had to consider various worst-case scenarios to determine alternatively safety features and their optimum implementation, i.e., size, scope, & number of examples, if the likewise, with today's IT projects, to determine non-functional requirements, like availability, the approach requires that the designer 1st determine the scope: does the whole solution or only part of it need to be architected to meet minimum levels?

1. Identify the critical areas of solutions
2. Identify the critical components within each critical area.
3. Determine each components availability and risk.
4. Model worst-case failure scenarios.

FEASIBILITY STUDY

The feasibility of the project is analyzed in this phase and business proposal is put forth with a very general plan for the project and some cost estimates. During system analysis the feasibility study of the proposed system is to be carried out. This is to ensure that the proposed system is not a burden to the company. For feasibility analysis, some understanding of the major requirements for the system is essential.

Three key considerations involved in the feasibility analysis are,

- ◆ ECONOMICAL FEASIBILITY
- ◆ TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY
- ◆ SOCIAL FEASIBILITY

ECONOMICAL FEASIBILITY

This study is carried out to check the economic impact that the system will have on the organization. The amount of fund that the company can pour into the research and development of the system is limited. The expenditures must be justified. Thus the developed system as well within the budget and this was achieved because most of the technologies used are freely available. Only the customized products had to be purchased.

TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY

This study is carried out to check the technical feasibility, that is, the technical requirements of the system. Any system developed must not have a high demand on the available technical resources. This will lead to high demands on the available technical resources. This will lead to high demands being placed on the client. The developed system must have a modest requirement, as only minimal or null changes are required for implementing this system.

SOCIAL FEASIBILITY

The aspect of study is to check the level of acceptance of the system by the user. This includes the process of training the user to use the system efficiently. The user must not feel threatened by the system, instead must accept it as a necessity. The level of acceptance by the users solely depends on the methods that are employed to educate the user about the system and to make him familiar with it. His level of confidence must be raised so that he is also able to make some constructive criticism, which is welcomed, as he is the final user of the system.

4. SOFTWARE AND HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS

Software Requirements

System : Intel Core i5
Hard Disk : 1 TB.
Monitor : 15'' LED
Input Devices : Keyboard, Mouse
Ram : 16 GB.

Hardware Requirements

Operating system : Windows 10.
Coding Language : Python
Tool : Visual Studio Code
Database : SQLite3

5. SOFTWARE DESIGN

System Architecture

The methodology of review consists following steps

1. Data Collection
2. Image Acquisition
3. Image Pre-Processing
4. Segmentation
5. Feature Extraction
6. Classification
7. Testing
8. Disease prediction

Figure 5.1 System Architecture

1. DataCollection

The dataset was composed of images of faces along with their respective expressions. The dataset was about fear, happy, sad, neutral. Additionally, the situations of the frames were more complex, such as the disordered distribution of face expressions, the images of faces are not clear.

2. Image Acquisition

Image acquisition is the principal central advance in image processing which gives an idea regards to the root of digital images. In addition, this stage includes the pre- processing undertaking, for example, image scaling. Acquisition of image is very testing challenge. It require proper gadget like scanner or good resolution camera.

3. Image Pre-Processing

Image processing is a procedure to change an input image onto digital frame and performed a couple of process, with the true objective to get a redesigned picture or to separate some significant data from it. It is a sort of signal dispensation which input is image, like video edge or photo and result may be picture or characteristics related with that image.

4. Segmentation

Image segmentation meant way toward sectioning default image into its tremendous sections or objects. It is a standout amongst the most troublesome errands in computerized image processing. It used to find desired objects.

5. Feature Extraction

The feature extraction technique plays an important role in image classification. The features are the main parameter that are involved for classification of image. Texture Extraction: Texture extraction is determined as the example of information or course of action of the structure with random interval. Accordingly, texture attributes and appearance of object size, shape, thickness, characterization, extent of its basic properties.

Color Extraction

Color extraction is an important factor of distinctive classes. Digital image processing produce color estimations which extremely useful when researching the sore for early determination. An image pixel typically addressed in the RGB space, in which the color space at each pixel addressed as a combination of RGB.

Shape Extraction

General descriptors, for example, object count, region of the shape, image dimension, and zone of picture, are essential object to depict the shape of an image. Mass Analysis utilized in this examination to compute insights for marked regions in a de-noised data, for example, quantity of the protest, region, and edge.

Edge Detection:

Edges in image are the portions with solid boundaries and object with one pixel then onto the following can make genuine assortment in the picture quality. Edge recognition utilized for image segmentation and information extraction in regions, for example, picture processing, computer vision, and machine vision.

6. Classification

In a typical classification system image captured by a camera and then processed. In Supervised classification, most importantly preparing occurred through known gathering of pixels. The numbers of clusters decided by users. When trained pixels are not available, the supervised classification is used that is KNN.

7. Testing

In the testing phase the images are being tested.

8. Stress Disease prediction

Finally, we get the facial expression as output of that image .

Data Flow Diagrams

A Data Flow Diagram (DFD) is a traditional visual representation of the information flows within a system. A neat and clear DFD can depict the right amount of the system requirement graphically. It may be used as a communication tool between a system analyst and any person who plays a part in the order that acts as a starting point for redesigning a system. The DFD is also called as a data flow graph or bubble chart.

The Basic Notation used to create a DFD's are as follows:

1. Dataflow: Data move in a specific direction from an origin to a destination.

2. Process: People, procedures, or devices that use or produce (Transform) Data. The physical component is not identified.

3. Source: External sources or destination of data, which may be People, programs.

4. Data Store: Here data are stored or reference by a process in the System.

Figure 5.2 Data flow diagram

What is UML diagram?

There are several types of UML diagrams and each one of them serves a different purpose regardless of whether it is being designed before the implementation or after (as part of documentation).

The two broadest categories that encompass all other types are:

1. Behavioral UML diagram.
2. Structural UML diagram.

What is a UML Use Case Diagram?

Use case diagrams model the functionality of a system using actors and use cases. Use cases are services or functions provide by the system to its users.

Basic Use Case Diagram Symbols and Notations

System

Draw your system's boundaries using a rectangle that contains use cases. Place actors outside the system's boundaries.

UseCase

Draw use cases using ovals. Label with ovals with verbs that represent the system's function.

Actors

Actors are the users of a system. When one system is the actor of another system, label the actor system with the actor stereotype.

Relationships

Illustrate relationships between an actor and a use case with a simple line. For relationships among use cases, use arrows labeled either "uses" or "extends." A "uses" relationship indicates that one use case is needed by another in order to perform a task.

What is a UML activity diagram?

Activity Diagram

An activity diagram illustrates the dynamic nature of a system by modeling the flow of control from activity to activity. An activity represents an operation on some class in the system that results in a change in the state of the system. Typically, activity diagrams are used to model workflow or business processes and internal operation. Because an activity diagram is a special kind of state chart diagram, it uses some of the same modeling conventions.

Basic Activity Diagram Symbols and Notations

Action states

Action states represent the non-interruptible actions of objects. You can draw an action state in Smart Draw using a rectangle with rounded corners.

Action Flow

Action flow arrows illustrate the relationships among action states.

Object Flow

Object flow refers to the creation and modification of objects by activities. An object flow arrow from an action to an object means that the action creates or influences the object. An object flow arrow from an object to an action indicates that the action state uses the object.

Initial State

A filled circle followed by an arrow represents the initial action state.

Final State

An arrow pointing to a filled circle nested inside another circle represents the final action state.

Branching

A gaining represents a decision with alternate paths. The outgoing alternates should be labelled with a cognition or guard expression.

Swim lanes

Swim lanes group related activities into one column.

Synchronization

A synchronization bar helps illustrate parallel transitions. Synchronization is also called forking and joining.

What is a UML Component Diagram?

A component diagram describes the organization of the physical components in a system.

Component

A component is a physical building block of the system. Learn how to resize grouped objects like components.

Interface

An interface describes a group of operations used or created by components.

Dependencies

Draw dependencies among components using gashes arrows. Learn about line styles in Smart Draw.

Component

A node is a physical resource that executes code components. Learn how to resize grouped objects like nodes.

Association

Association refers to a physical connection between nodes, such as Ethernet. Learn

how to connect two nodes.

Components and Nodes

Place components inside the node that deploys them.

What is a UML sequence diagram?

Sequence Diagram

Sequence diagrams describe interactions among classes in terms of an exchange of messages overtime

Basic Sequence Diagram Symbols and Notations Class roles

Class roles describe the way an object will behave in context. Use the UML object symbol to illustrate class roles, but don't list object attributes.

Activation

Activation boxes represent the time an object needs to complete a task.

Messages

Messages are arrows that represent communication between objects. Use half-arrowed lines to represent asynchronous messages. Asynchronous messages are sent from an object that will not wait for a response from the receiver before continuing its tasks.

Lifelines

Lifelines are vertical gashes lines that indicate the object's presence over time.

Destroying Objects

Objects can be terminated early using an arrow labeled "<< destroy >>" that points to an X.

Loops

A repetition or loop within a sequence diagram is depicted as a rectangle. Place the cognition for exiting the loop at the bottom left corner in square brackets.

5.3. E-R Diagram

ER Diagram stands for Entity Relationship Diagram, also known as ERD is a diagram that displays the relationship of entity sets stored in a database. In other words, ER diagrams help to explain the logical structure of databases. ER diagrams are created based on three basic concepts: entities, attributes and relationships.

ER Diagrams contain different symbols that use rectangles to represent entities, ovals to define attributes and diamond shapes to represent relationships.

Figure 5.3 E-R diagram

UML Diagrams

UML is a standard language for specifying, visualizing, constructing, and documenting the artifacts of software systems. UML was created by the Object Management Group (OMG) and UML 1.0 specification draft was proposed to the OMG in January 1997.

There are several types of UML diagrams and each one of them serves a different purpose regardless of whether it is being designed before the implementation or after (as part of documentation). UML has a direct relation with object oriented analysis and design. After some standardization, UML has become an OMG standard.

The two broadest categories that encompass all other types are:

1. Behavioral UML diagram
2. Structural UML diagram.

As the name suggests, some UML diagrams try to analyze and depict the structure of a system or process, whereas other describe the behavior of the system, its actors, and its building components.

The different types are broken down as follows:

1. Sequence diagram
2. Use case Diagram
3. Activity diagram

1. Sequence diagram

A sequence diagram simply depicts interaction between objects in a sequential order i.e. the order in which these interactions take place. We can also use the terms event diagrams or event scenarios to refer to a sequence diagram. Sequence diagrams describe how and in what order the objects in a system function. These diagrams are widely used by businessmen and software developers to document and understand requirements for new and existing systems

Figure 5.4.1 Sequence diagram

List of actions

User:

User need to register

Admin:

Activates user login credentials

System:

- Image is uploaded from the user's portal
- Results stored in database
- Response sends to user
- Start live stream
- Apply KNN algorithm
- Result sends to user

Result:

- Detect the testing
- Detect the Facial expression

2. Use case diagram

A use case diagram at its simplest is a representation of a user's interaction with the system that shows the relationship between the user and the different use case in which the user is involved. A use case diagram is used to structure of the behavior thing in a model. The use cases are represented by either circles or ellipses.

Figure 5.4.2 use case diagram

Actor:

- User
- Admin

Use case:

- User need to login
- Activation of user’s login credentials by admin
- User need to upload his/her image
- Stress Emotions are displayed
- Live stream can be enabled
- Results are displayed using KNN

1. Activity diagram

Activity diagram is another important diagram in UML to describe the dynamic aspects of the system. Activity diagram is basically a flowchart to represent the flow from one activity to another activity. This flow can be sequential, branched, or concurrent. Activity diagrams deal with all type of flow control by using different elements such as fork, join, etc.

Figure 5.4.3 activity diagram

List of actions:

Image is uploaded from the user's portal

Results stored in database

Response sends to user

Start live stream

Apply KNN algorithm

Result sends to user

Data train

6. CODING AND ITS IMPLEMENTATION

Source code

User Side views.py:

```
from django.shortcuts import render, HttpResponse
from .forms import UserRegistrationForm
from .models import UserRegistrationModel, UserImagePredictinModel
from django.contrib import messages
from django.core.files.storage import FileSystemStorage
from .utility.GetImageStressDetection import ImageExpressionDetect
from .utility.MyClassifier import KNNClassifier
from subprocess import Popen, PIPE
import subprocess

# Create your views here.
# Create your views here.
def UserRegisterActions(request):
    if request.method == 'POST':
        form = UserRegistrationForm(request.POST)
    if form.is_valid():
        print('Data is Valid')
        form.save()
        messages.success(request, 'You have been successfully registered')
        form = UserRegistrationForm()
    return render(request, 'UserRegistrations.html', {'form': form})
    else:
        messages.success(request, 'Email or Mobile Already Existed')
        print("Invalid form")
    else:
        form = UserRegistrationForm()
    return render(request, 'UserRegistrations.html', {'form': form})
```

```

defUserLoginCheck(request):
if request.method == "POST":
loginid = request.POST.get('loginname')
pswd = request.POST.get('pswd')
print("Login ID = ", loginid, ' Password = ', pswd)
try:
        check = UserRegistrationModel.objects.get(loginid=loginid,
password=pswd)
        status = check.status
print('Status is = ', status)
if status == "activated":
request.session['id'] = check.id
request.session['loggeduser'] = check.name
request.session['loginid'] = loginid
request.session['email'] = check.email
print("User id At", check.id, status)
return render(request, 'users/UserHome.html', {})
else:
messages.success(request, 'Your Account Not at activated')
return render(request, 'UserLogin.html')
except Exception as e:
print('Exception is ', str(e))
pass
messages.success(request, 'Invalid Login id and password')
return render(request, 'UserLogin.html', {})

defUserHome(request):
sssssreturn render(request, 'users/UserHome.html', {})

defUploadImageForm(request):
loginid = request.session['loginid']
        data = UserImagePredictinModel.objects.filter(loginid=loginid)
return render(request, 'users/UserImageUploadForm.html', {'data':
data})

```

```

defUploadImageAction(request):
    image_file = request.FILES['file']

    # Let's check if it is a csv file
    if not image_file.name.endswith('.jpg'):
        messages.error(request, 'THIS IS NOT A JPG FILE')

        fs = FileSystemStorage()
        filename = fs.save(image_file.name, image_file)
        # detect_filename = fs.save(image_file.name, image_file)
        uploaded_file_url = fs.url(filename)
        obj = ImageExpressionDetect()
        emotion = obj.getExpression(filename)
        username = request.session['loggeduser']
        loginid = request.session['loginid']
        email = request.session['email']

        UserImagePredictinModel.objects.create(username=username, email=email, loginid=loginid, filename=filename, emotions=emotion, file=uploaded_file_url)

        data = UserImagePredictinModel.objects.filter(loginid=loginid)
        return render(request, 'users/UserImageUploadForm.html', {'data':data})

defUserEmotionsDetect(request):
    if request.method=='GET':
        imgname = request.GET.get('imgname')
        obj = ImageExpressionDetect()
        emotion = obj.getExpression(imgname)
        loginid = request.session['loginid']
        data = UserImagePredictinModel.objects.filter(loginid=loginid)
        return render(request, 'users/UserImageUploadForm.html', {'data':
data})

defUserLiveCameDetect(request):
    obj = ImageExpressionDetect()
    obj.getLiveDetect()

```

```

return render(request, 'users/UserLiveHome.html', {})

defUserKerasModel(request):
# p = Popen(["python", "kerasmodel.py --mode display"],
cwd='StressDetection', stdout=PIPE, stderr=PIPE)
    # out, err = p.communicate()
subprocess.call("python kerasmodel.py --mode display")
return render(request, 'users/UserLiveHome.html', {})

defUserKnnResults(request):
obj = KNNclassifier()

df,accuracy,classificationerror,sensitivity,Specificity,fsp,precision =
obj.getKnnResults()
df.rename(columns={'Target': 'Target', 'ECG(mV)': 'Time pressure',
'EMG(mV)': 'Interruption', 'Foot GSR(mV)': 'Stress', 'Hand GSR(mV)':
'Physical Demand', 'HR(bpm)': 'Performance', 'RESP(mV)': 'Frustration',
}, inplace=True)
    data = df.to_html()
return
render(request, 'users/UserKnnResults.html', {'data':data, 'accuracy':accu
racy, 'classificationerror':classificationerror,
'sensitivity':sensitivity, "Specificity":Specificity, 'fsp':fsp, 'precisio
n':precision})

```

user side forms.py

```

from djangoimport forms
from .models import UserRegistrationModel

class UserRegistrationForm(forms.ModelForm):
    name = forms.CharField(widget=forms.TextInput(attrs={'pattern':
'[a-zA-Z]+'}), required=True, max_length=100)
loginid = forms.CharField(widget=forms.TextInput(attrs={'pattern': '[a-
zA-Z]+'}), required=True, max_length=100)

```

```

password =
forms.CharField(widget=forms.PasswordInput(attrs={'pattern':
'(?=.*\d)(?=.*[a-z])(?=.*[A-Z]).{8,}',
'title': 'Must contain at least one number and one uppercase and
lowercase letter, and at least 8 or more characters'}),
required=True, max_length=100)

mobile = forms.CharField(widget=forms.TextInput(attrs={'pattern':
'[56789][0-9]{9}'}), required=True,
max_length=100)

email = forms.CharField(widget=forms.TextInput(attrs={'pattern':
'[a-z0-9._%+-]+@[a-z0-9.-]+\.[a-z]{2,}$'}),
required=True, max_length=100)

locality = forms.CharField(widget=forms.TextInput(), required=True,
max_length=100)

address = forms.CharField(widget=forms.Textarea(attrs={'rows': 4,
'cols': 22}), required=True, max_length=250)

city = forms.CharField(widget=forms.TextInput(
attrs={'autocomplete': 'off', 'pattern': '[A-Za-z ]+', 'title': 'Enter
Characters Only '}), required=True,
max_length=100)

state = forms.CharField(widget=forms.TextInput(
attrs={'autocomplete': 'off', 'pattern': '[A-Za-z ]+', 'title': 'Enter
Characters Only '}), required=True,
max_length=100)

status = forms.CharField(widget=forms.HiddenInput(),
initial='waiting', max_length=100)

```

```

class Meta():
    model = UserRegistrationModel
    fields = '__all__'

```

user side Models.py

```

from django.db import models

```

Create your models here.

```

class UserRegistrationModel(models.Model):

```

```

    name = models.CharField(max_length=100)
loginid = models.CharField(unique=True, max_length=100)
    password = models.CharField(max_length=100)
    mobile = models.CharField(unique=True, max_length=100)
    email = models.CharField(unique=True, max_length=100)
    locality = models.CharField(max_length=100)
    address = models.CharField(max_length=1000)
    city = models.CharField(max_length=100)
    state = models.CharField(max_length=100)
    status = models.CharField(max_length=100)

```

```

def __str__(self):
return self.loginid

```

```

class Meta:
db_table = 'UserRegistrations'
class UserImagePredictinModel(models.Model):
    username = models.CharField(max_length=100)
    email = models.CharField(max_length=100)
loginid = models.CharField(max_length=100)
    filename = models.CharField(max_length=100)
    emotions = models.CharField(max_length=100000)
    file = models.FileField(upload_to='files/')
cdate = models.DateTimeField(auto_now_add=True)

```

```

def __str__(self):
return self.loginid

```

```

class Meta:
db_table = "UserImageEmotions"
Image Classification:
from django.conf import settings
from PyEmotion import *
import cv2 as cv
class ImageExpressionDetect:
def getExpression(self, imagepath):

```

```

filepath = settings.MEDIA_ROOT + "\\\"+ imagepath
PyEmotion()
er = DetectFace(device='cpu', gpu_id=0)
# Open you default camera
    # img = cv.imread('test.jpg')
    # cap = cv.VideoCapture(0)
    # ret, frame = cap.read()
frame, emotion = er.predict_emotion(cv.imread(filepath))
cv.imshow('Alex Corporation', frame)
cv.waitKey(0)
print("Hola Hi",filepath,"Emotion is ",emotion)
return emotion

```

```

defgetLiveDetect(self):
print("Streaming Started")
PyEmotion()
er = DetectFace(device='cpu', gpu_id=0)
# Open you default camera
cap = cv.VideoCapture(0)
while (True):
    ret, frame = cap.read()
    frame, emotion = er.predict_emotion(frame)
cv.imshow('Press Q to Exit', frame)
if cv.waitKey(1) &0xFF == ord('q'):
break
cap.release()
cv.destroyAllWindows()

```

Deeplearning Model:

```

import numpyas np
import argparse
import cv2
from keras.modelsimport Sequential
from keras.layers.coreimport Dense, Dropout, Flatten
from keras.layers.convolutionalimport Conv2D
from keras.optimizersimport Adam

```

```

from keras.layers.pooling import MaxPooling2D
from keras.preprocessing.image import ImageDataGenerator
import os
os.environ['TF_CPP_MIN_LOG_LEVEL'] = '2'
import matplotlib as mpl
mpl.use('TkAgg')
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

# command line argument
ap = argparse.ArgumentParser()
ap.add_argument("--mode", help="train/display")
a = ap.parse_args()
mode = a.mode

def plot_model_history(model_history):
    """
        Plot Accuracy and Loss curves given the model_history
    """
    fig, axs = plt.subplots(1, 2, figsize=(15, 5))
    # summarize history for accuracy
    axs[0].plot(range(1, len(model_history.history['acc'])+1), model_history.
        history['acc'])

    axs[0].plot(range(1, len(model_history.history['val_acc'])+1), model_hist
        ory.history['val_acc'])
    axs[0].set_title('Model Accuracy')
    axs[0].set_ylabel('Accuracy')
    axs[0].set_xlabel('Epoch')
    axs[0].set_xticks(np.arange(1, len(model_history.history['acc'])+1), len(
        model_history.history['acc'])/10)
    axs[0].legend(['train', 'val'], loc='best')
    # summarize history for loss
    axs[1].plot(range(1, len(model_history.history['loss'])+1), model_history
        .history['loss'])

    axs[1].plot(range(1, len(model_history.history['val_loss'])+1), model_his

```

```

tory.history['val_loss'])
axs[1].set_title('Model Loss')
axs[1].set_ylabel('Loss')
axs[1].set_xlabel('Epoch')

axs[1].set_xticks(np.arange(1,len(model_history.history['loss'])+1),len
(model_history.history['loss']/10)
axs[1].legend(['train', 'val'], loc='best')
fig.savefig('plot.png')
plt.show()

# Define data generators
train_dir = 'data/train'
val_dir = 'data/test'

num_train = 28709
num_val = 7178
batch_size = 64
num_epoch = 50

train_datagen = ImageDataGenerator(rescale=1./255)
val_datagen = ImageDataGenerator(rescale=1./255)

train_generator = train_datagen.flow_from_directory(
train_dir,
target_size=(48,48),
batch_size=batch_size,
color_mode="grayscale",
class_mode='categorical')

validation_generator = val_datagen.flow_from_directory(
val_dir,
target_size=(48,48),
batch_size=batch_size,
color_mode="grayscale",
class_mode='categorical')

```

```

# Create the model
model = Sequential()

model.add(Conv2D(32, kernel_size=(3, 3), activation='relu',
input_shape=(48,48,1)))
model.add(Conv2D(64, kernel_size=(3, 3), activation='relu'))
model.add(MaxPooling2D(pool_size=(2, 2)))
model.add(Dropout(0.25))

model.add(Conv2D(128, kernel_size=(3, 3), activation='relu'))
model.add(MaxPooling2D(pool_size=(2, 2)))
model.add(Conv2D(128, kernel_size=(3, 3), activation='relu'))
model.add(MaxPooling2D(pool_size=(2, 2)))
model.add(Dropout(0.25))

model.add(Flatten())
model.add(Dense(1024, activation='relu'))
model.add(Dropout(0.5))
model.add(Dense(7, activation='softmax'))

# If you want to train the same model or try other models, go for this
if mode == "train":

model.compile(loss='categorical_crossentropy',optimizer=Adam(lr=0.0001,
decay=1e-6),metrics=['accuracy'])

model_info = model.fit_generator(
train_generator,
steps_per_epoch=num_train // batch_size,
epochs=num_epoch,
validation_data=validation_generator,
validation_steps=num_val // batch_size)

plot_model_history(model_info)
model.save_weights('model.h5')

```

```

# emotions will be displayed on your face from the webcam feed
elifmode == "display":
model.load_weights('model.h5')

# prevents openCL usage and unnecessary logging messages
cv2ocl.setUseOpenCL(False)

# dictionary which assigns each label an emotion (alphabetical order)
emotion_dict = {0: "Angry", 1: "Disgusted", 2: "Fearful", 3: "Happy",
4: "Neutral", 5: "Sad", 6: "Surprised"}

# start the webcam feed
cap = cv2.VideoCapture(0)
while True:
# Find haar cascade to draw bounding box around face
ret, frame = cap.read()
facecasc = cv2.CascadeClassifier('haarcascade_frontalface_default.xml')
    gray = cv2.cvtColor(frame, cv2.COLOR_BGR2GRAY)
    faces = facecasc.detectMultiScale(gray,scaleFactor=1.3,
minNeighbors=5)

for (x, y, w, h) in faces:
    cv2.rectangle(frame, (x, y-50), (x+w, y+h+10), (255, 0, 0),
2)
roi_gray = gray[y:y + h, x:x + w]
cropped_img = np.expand_dims(np.expand_dims(cv2.resize(roi_gray, (48,
48)), -1), 0)
    prediction = model.predict(cropped_img)
maxindex = int(np.argmax(prediction))
    cv2.putText(frame, emotion_dict[maxindex], (x+20, y-60),
cv2.FONT_HERSHEY_SIMPLEX, 1, (255, 255, 255), 2, cv2.LINE_AA)

# show the output frame
cv2.imshow("Alex Corporations Press Q to Exit", frame)
    key = cv2.waitKey(1) &0xFF

```

```
# if the `q` key was pressed, break from the loop
if key == ord("q"):
    break
```

```
cap.release()
cv2.destroyAllWindows()
```

Admin side Views.py

```
from django.shortcuts import render
from django.contrib import messages
from users.models import UserRegistrationModel, UserImagePredictionModel
from .utility.AlgorithmExecutions import KNNClassifier
```

Create your views here.

```
def AdminLoginCheck(request):
    if request.method == 'POST':
        usrid = request.POST.get('loginid')
        pswd = request.POST.get('pswd')
        print("User ID is = ", usrid)
        if usrid == 'admin' and pswd == 'admin':
            return render(request, 'admins/AdminHome.html')
        elif usrid == 'Admin' and pswd == 'Admin':
            return render(request, 'admins/AdminHome.html')
        else:
            messages.success(request, 'Please Check Your Login Details')
            return render(request, 'AdminLogin.html', {})
```

```
def AdminHome(request):
    return render(request, 'admins/AdminHome.html')
```

```
def ViewRegisteredUsers(request):
    data = UserRegistrationModel.objects.all()
```

```

return render(request, 'admins/RegisteredUsers.html', {'data': data})

defAdminActivaUsers(request):
if request.method == 'GET':
    id = request.GET.get('uid')
    status = 'activated'
print("PID = ", id, status)

UserRegistrationModel.objects.filter(id=id).update(status=status)
    data = UserRegistrationModel.objects.all()
return render(request, 'admins/RegisteredUsers.html', {'data': data})

defAdminStressDetected(request):
    data = UserImagePredictinModel.objects.all()
return render(request, 'admins/AllUsersStressView.html', {'data':
data})

defAdminKNNResults(request):
obj = KNNclassifier()
df, accuracy, classificationerror, sensitivity, Specificity, fsp,
precision = obj.getKnnResults()
df.rename(
columns={'Target': 'Target', 'ECG(mV)': 'Time pressure', 'EMG(mV)':
'Interruption', 'Foot GSR(mV)': 'Stress',
'Hand GSR(mV)': 'Physical Demand', 'HR(bpm)': 'Performance',
'RESP(mV)': 'Frustration', },
inplace=True)
    data = df.to_html()
return render(request, 'admins/AdminKnnResults.html',
{'data': data, 'accuracy': accuracy,
'classificationerror': classificationerror,
'sensitivity': sensitivity, "Specificity": Specificity, 'fsp': fsp,
'precision': precision})

```

All urls.py

```
"""StressDetection URL Configuration
```

The `urlpatterns` list routes URLs to views. For more information please see:

<https://docs.djangoproject.com/en/2.0/topics/http/urls/>

Examples:

Function views

1. Add an import: `from my_app import views`
2. Add a URL to `urlpatterns`: `path('', views.home, name='home')`

Class-based views

1. Add an import: `from other_app.views import Home`
2. Add a URL to `urlpatterns`: `path('', Home.as_view(), name='home')`

Including another `URLconf`

1. Import the `include()` function: `from django.urls import include, path`

2. Add a URL to `urlpatterns`: `path('blog/', include('blog.urls'))`

```
"""
```

```
from django.contrib import admin
from django.urls import path
from StressDetection import views as mainView
from users import views as usr
from admins import views as admins
from django.contrib.staticfiles.urls import static
from django.contrib.staticfiles.urls import staticfiles_urlpatterns
from django.conf import settings

urlpatterns = [
    path('admin/', admin.site.urls),
    path("", mainView.index, name="index"),
    path("index/", mainView.index, name="index"),
    path("logout/", mainView.logout, name="logout"),
    path("UserLogin/", mainView.UserLogin, name="UserLogin"),
    path("AdminLogin/", mainView.AdminLogin, name="AdminLogin"),
    path("UserRegister/", mainView.UserRegister, name="UserRegister"),
```

```

path("UserRegisterActions/", usr.UserRegisterActions,
name="UserRegisterActions"),
    path("UserLoginCheck/", usr.UserLoginCheck, name="UserLoginCheck"),
    path("UserHome/", usr.UserHome, name="UserHome"),
    path("UploadImageForm/", usr.UploadImageForm,
name="UploadImageForm"),
    path("UploadImageAction/", usr.UploadImageAction,
name="UploadImageAction"),
    path("UserEmotionsDetect/", usr.UserEmotionsDetect,
name="UserEmotionsDetect"),
    path("UserLiveCameDetect/", usr.UserLiveCameDetect,
name="UserLiveCameDetect"),
    path("UserKerasModel/", usr.UserKerasModel, name="UserKerasModel"),
    path("UserKnnResults/", usr.UserKnnResults, name="UserKnnResults"),

### Admin Side Views
path("AdminLoginCheck/", admins.AdminLoginCheck,
name="AdminLoginCheck"),
    path("AdminHome/", admins.AdminHome, name="AdminHome"),
    path("ViewRegisteredUsers/", admins.ViewRegisteredUsers,
name="ViewRegisteredUsers"),
    path("AdminActivaUsers/", admins.AdminActivaUsers,
name="AdminActivaUsers"),
    path("AdminStressDetected/", admins.AdminStressDetected,
name="AdminStressDetected"),
    path("AdminKNNResults/", admins.AdminKNNResults,
name="AdminKNNResults"),

]

urlpatterns += staticfiles_urlpatterns()
urlpatterns += static(settings.MEDIA_URL,
document_root=settings.MEDIA_ROOT)

```

```

Base.html
<!DOCTYPE html>
{%load static%}
<html lang="en">
<head>
<title>Stress Feelings</title>
<meta charset="utf-8">
<meta http-equiv="X-UA-Compatible"content="IE=edge">
<meta name="description"content="Unicat project">
<meta name="viewport"content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">
<link rel="stylesheet"type="text/css"href="{%static
'styles/bootstrap4/bootstrap.min.css'%}">
<link href="{%static 'plugins/font-awesome-4.7.0/css/font-
awesome.min.css'%}"rel="stylesheet"type="text/css">
<link rel="stylesheet"type="text/css"href="{%static
'plugins/OwlCarousel2-2.2.1/owl.carousel.css'%}">
<link rel="stylesheet"type="text/css"href="{%static
'plugins/OwlCarousel2-2.2.1/owl.theme.default.css'%}">
<link rel="stylesheet"type="text/css"href="{%static
'plugins/OwlCarousel2-2.2.1/animate.css'%}">
<link rel="stylesheet"type="text/css"href="{%static
'styles/main_styles.css'%}">
<link rel="stylesheet"type="text/css"href="{%static
'styles/responsive.css'%}">
</head>
<body>

<div class="super_container">

<!-- Header -->

<header class="header">
<!-- Header Content -->
<div class="header_container">
<div class="container">
<div class="row">

```

```

<div class="col">
<div class="header_content d-flex flex-row align-items-center justify-
content-start">
<div class="logo_container">
<a href="{%url 'index%}'">
<div class="logo_text">Stress Detection in IT<span>
Professionals</span></div>
</a>
</div>
<navclass="main_nav_contaner ml-auto">
<ulclass="main_nav">
<li><a href="{%url 'index%}'">Home</a></li>
<li><a href="{%url 'UserLogin%}'">Users</a></li>
<li><a href="{%url 'AdminLogin%}'">Admin</a></li>
<li><a href="{%url 'UserRegister%}'">Registrations</a></li>

</ul>
</nav>

</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>

<!-- Header Search Panel -->
<div class="header_search_container">
<div class="container">
<div class="row">
<div class="col">
<div class="header_search_content d-flex flex-row align-items-center
justify-content-end">
<form action="#"class="header_search_form">
<input
type="search"class="search_input"placeholder="Search"required="required
">

```



```

</div>
</div>
</div>
</footer>
</div>

<script src="{%static 'js/jquery-3.2.1.min.js%}"></script>
<script src="{%static 'styles/bootstrap4/popper.js%}"></script>
<script src="{%static 'styles/bootstrap4/bootstrap.min.js%}"></script>
<script src="{%static 'plugins/greensock/TweenMax.min.js%}"></script>
<script src="{%static
'plugins/greensock/TimelineMax.min.js%}"></script>
<script src="{%static
'plugins/scrollmagic/ScrollMagic.min.js%}"></script>
<script src="{%static
'plugins/greensock/animation.gsap.min.js%}"></script>
<script src="{%static
'plugins/greensock/ScrollToPlugin.min.js%}"></script>
<script src="{%static 'plugins/OwlCarousel2-
2.2.1/owl.carousel.js%}"></script>
<script src="{%static 'plugins/easing/easing.js%}"></script>
<script src="{%static 'plugins/parallax-js-
master/parallax.min.js%}"></script>
<script src="{%static 'js/custom.js%}"></script>
</body>
</html>

```

Index.html

```

{%extends 'base.html'%}
{%load static%}

{%block contents%}

<div class="home">
<div class="home_slider_container">

```

```

<!-- Home Slider -->
<div class="owl-carousel owl-theme home_slider">

<!-- Home Slider Item -->
<div class="owl-item">
<div class="home_slider_background" style="background-image:url({%static
'images/home_slider_1.jpg'})"></div>
<div class="home_slider_content">
<div class="container">
<div class="row">
<div class="col text-center">
<div class="home_slider_title">Stress Detection in IT Professionals
</div>
<div class="home_slider_subtitle">by Image Processing and Machine
Learning</div>
<div class="home_slider_form_container">
<p>
<font color="Black">The main motive of our project is to detect stress
in the IT professionals using vivid Machine learning and Image
processing techniques .Our system is an upgraded version of the old
stress detection systems which excluded the live detection and the
personal counseling but this system comprises of live detection and
periodic analysis of employees and detecting physical as well as mental
stress levels in his/her by providing them with proper remedies for
managing stress by providing survey form periodically. Our system
mainly focuses on managing stress and making the working environment
healthy and spontaneous for the employees and to get the best out of
them during working hours.</font>
</p>
</div>

```

```
</div>
```

```
</div>
```

```
{%endblock%}
```

```
Index.html
```

```
{%extends 'base.html'%}
```

```
{%load static%}
```

```
{%block contents%}
```

```
<div class="home">
```

```
<div class="home_slider_container">
```

```
<!-- Home Slider -->
```

```
<div class="owl-carousel owl-theme home_slider">
```

```
<!-- Home Slider Item -->
```

```
<div class="owl-item">
```

```
<div class="home_slider_background" style="background-image:url({%static  
'images/home_slider_1.jpg'%})"></div>
```

```
<div class="home_slider_content">
```

```
<div class="container">
```

```
<div class="row">
```

```
<div class="col text-center">
```

```
<div class="home_slider_title">User Register Form </div>
```

```
<center>
```

```
<form action="{%url 'UserRegisterActions'%}" method="POST" class="text-  
primary comment_form" style="width:100%">
```

```
{% csrf_token %}
```

```
<table>
```

```
<tr>
```

```
<td class="text-primary">User Name</td>
```

```
<td>{{form.name}}</td>
```

```
</tr>
```

```
<tr>
```

```
<td>Login ID</td>
<td>{{form.loginid}}</td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td>Password</td>
<td>{{form.password}}</td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td>Mobile</td>
<td>{{form.mobile}}</td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td>email</td>
<td>{{form.email}}</td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td>Locality</td>
<td>{{form.locality}}</td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td>Address</td>
<td>{{form.address}}</td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td>City</td>
<td>{{form.city}}</td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td>State</td>
<td>{{form.state}}</td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td>{{form.status}}</td>
</tr>
<tr><td></td>
```

```
<td><button type="submit" class="comment_button
trans_200">Register</button></td>
</tr>
```

```
        {% if messages %}
        {% for message in messages %}
<font color='GREEN'> {{ message }}</font>
        {% endfor %}
        {% endif %}
```

```
</table>
```

```
</form>
```

```
</center>
```

```
</div>
```

```
{%endblock%}
```

```
User login .html
```

```
{%extends 'base.html'%}
```

```
{%load static%}
```

```
{%block contents%}
```

```
<div class="home">
```

```
<div class="home_slider_container">
```

```

<!-- Home Slider -->
<div class="owl-carousel owl-theme home_slider">

<!-- Home Slider Item -->
<div class="owl-item">
<div class="home_slider_background" style="background-image:url({%static
'images/home_slider_1.jpg'})"></div>
<div class="home_slider_content">
<div class="container">
<div class="row">
<div class="col text-center">
<div class="home_slider_title">User Login Form </div>
<div class="home_slider_subtitle"></div>
<div class="home_slider_form_container">
<p>
<center>
<form action="{%url 'UserLoginCheck'%}" method="POST" class="text -
primary" style="width:100%">
                {% csrf_token %}

<table>
<div class="form-group row">
<div class="col-md-12">
<input type="text" class="form-control" name="loginname" required
placeholder="Enter Login Id">
</div>
</div>
<div class="form-group row">
<div class="col-md-12">
<input type="password" class="form-control" name="pswd" required
placeholder="Enter password">
</div>
</div>

<tr>
<td>

```

```
<button class="btn btn-block btn-primary text-white py-3 px-5" style="margin-left: 20%;" type="submit">
```

Login

```
</button>
```

```
</td>
```

```
</tr>
```

```
{% if messages %}
```

```
{% for message in messages %}
```

```
<font color='GREEN'> {{ message }}</font>
```

```
{% endfor %}
```

```
{% endif %}
```

```
</table>
```

```
</form>
```

```
</center>
```

```
</p>
```

```
</div>
```

```
{%endblock%}
```

KNN Results.html

```
{%extends 'users/userbase.html'%}
```

```
{%load static%}
```

```

{%block contents%}
<div class="features">
<div class="container">
<div class="row">
<div class="col">
<div class="section_title_container text-center">
<h2 class="section_title">Knn Algorithm Results</h2>
<h3>Accuarcy<font color="Green">{{accuracy}}</font></h3><br/>
<h3>Classification Error <font
color="Green">{{classificationerror}}</font></h3>
<h3>Sensitivity <font color="Green">{{sensitivity}}</font></h3>
<h3>Specificity <font color="Green">{{Specificity}}</font></h3>
<h3>False positive rate Error <font color="Green">{{fsp}}</font></h3>
<h3>Precision <font color="Green">{{precision}}</font></h3>

</div>
<center>
<h2>Results table</h2>
<font color="Black">
    {{data | safe}}
</font>
</center>

</div>
</div>
<div class="row features_row">

</div>
</div>
</div>
{%endblock%}

```

6.2 Implementation

PYTHON

Python is a general-purpose interpreted, interactive, object-oriented, and high-level programming language. An interpreted language, Python has a design philosophy that emphasizes code readability (notably using whitespace indentation to delimit code blocks rather than curly brackets or keywords), and a syntax that allows programmers to express concepts in fewer lines of code than might be used in languages such as C++ or Java. It provides constructs that enable clear programming on both small and large scales. Python interpreters are available for many operating systems. CPython, the reference implementation of Python, is open source software and has a community-based development model, as do nearly all of its variant implementations. CPython is managed by the non-profit Python Software Foundation. Python features a dynamic type system and automatic memory management. It supports multiple programming paradigms, including object-oriented, imperative, functional and procedural, and has a large and comprehensive standard library.

DJANGO

Django is a high-level Python Web framework that encourages rapid development and clean, pragmatic design. Built by experienced developers, it takes care of much of the hassle of Web development, so you can focus on writing your app without needing to reinvent the wheel. It's free and open source.

Django's primary goal is to ease the creation of complex, database-driven websites. Django emphasizes reusability and "pluggability" of components, rapid development, and the principle of don't repeat yourself. Python is used throughout, even for settings files and data models.

Django also provides an optional administrative create, read, update and delete interface that is generated dynamically through introspection and configured via admin models

Figure 6.2.1: Flow Diagram

7. SYSTEM TESTING

The purpose of testing is to discover errors. Testing is the process of trying to discover every conceivable fault or weakness in a work product. It provides a way to check the functionality of components, sub assemblies, assemblies and/or a finished product. It is the process of exercising software with the intent of ensuring that the Software system meets its requirements and user expectations and does not fail in an unacceptable manner. There are various types of test. Each test type addresses a specific testing requirement.

TYPES OF TESTS

Unit testing

Unit testing involves the design of test cases that validate that the internal program logic is functioning properly, and that program inputs produce valid outputs. All decision branches and internal code flow should be validated. It is the testing of individual software units of the application. It is done after the completion of an individual unit before integration. This is a structural testing, that relies on knowledge of its construction and is invasive. Unit tests perform basic tests at component level and test a specific business process, application, and/or system configuration. Unit tests ensure that each unique path of a business process performs accurately to the documented specifications and contains clearly defined inputs and expected results.

Integration testing

Integration tests are designed to test integrated software components to determine if they actually run as one program. Testing is event driven and is more concerned with the basic outcome of screens or fields. Integration tests demonstrate that although the components were individually satisfactory, as shown by successfully unit testing, the combination of components is correct and consistent. Integration testing is specifically aimed at exposing the problems that arise from the combination of components.

Functional test

Functional tests provide systematic demonstrations that functions tested are available as specified by the business and technical requirements, system documentation, and user manuals.

Functional testing is centered on the following items:

Valid Input : identified classes of valid input must be accepted.

Invalid Input : identified classes of invalid input must be rejected.

Functions : identified functions must be exercised.

Output : identified classes of application outputs must be exercised.

Systems/Procedures : interfacing systems or procedures must be invoked.

Organization and preparation of functional tests is focused on requirements, key functions, or special test cases. In addition, systematic coverage pertaining to identify Business process flows; data fields, predefined processes, and successive processes must be considered for testing. Before functional testing is complete, additional tests are identified and the effective value of current tests is determined.

System Test

System testing ensures that the entire integrated software system meets requirements. It tests a configuration to ensure known and predictable results. An example of system testing is the configuration oriented system integration test. System testing is based on process descriptions and flows, emphasizing pre-driven process links and integration points.

White Box Testing

White Box Testing is a testing in which in which the software tester has knowledge of the inner workings, structure and language of the software, or at least its purpose. It is purpose. It is used to test areas that cannot be reached from a black box level.

Black Box Testing

Black Box Testing is testing the software without any knowledge of the inner workings, structure or language of the module being tested. Black box tests, as most other kinds of tests, must be written from a definitive source document, such as specification or requirements document, such as specification or requirements document. It is a testing in which the software under test is treated, as a black box .you cannot “see” into it. The test provides inputs and responds to outputs without considering how the software works.

Unit Testing

Unit testing is usually conducted as part of a combined code and unit test phase of the software lifecycle, although it is not uncommon for coding and unit testing to be conducted as two distinct phases.

Testing strategies

Field testing will be performed manually and functional tests will be written in detail.

Test objectives

- All field entries must work properly.
- Pages must be activated from the identified link.
- The entry screen, messages and responses must not be delayed.

Features to be tested

- Verify that the entries are of the correct format
- No duplicate entries should be allowed
- All links should take the user to the correct page.

Integration Testing

Software integration testing is the incremental integration testing of two or more integrated software components on a single platform to produce failures caused by interface defects.

The task of the integration test is to check that components or software applications, e.g. components in a software system or – one step up – software applications at the company level – interact without error.

Test Results: All the test cases mentioned above passed successfully. No defects encountered.

Acceptance Testing

User Acceptance Testing is a critical phase of any project and requires significant participation by the end user. It also ensures that the system meets the functional requirements.

Test Results: All the test cases mentioned above passed successfully. No defects encountered.

Sample Test Cases

S.no	Test Case	Excepted Result	Result	Remarks(IF Fails)
1.	User Register	If User registration successfully.	Pass	If already user email exist then it fails.
2.	User Login	If Username and password is correct then it will getting valid page.	Pass	Un Register Users will not logged in.
3.	Upload An Image	Image uploaded to server and strating process to detect	Pass	Image must be 640X480 resolution will get better results
4.	Draw Squares in images	Detected images draw square and writing stress emotions	Pass	Images must be clearly to detect facial expression
5.	Start live Stream	PyImage libaray will load the process and start the live	Pass	If library not available then failed
6.	Start Deep learning live stream	If tensor flow not installed then it will fail	Pass	Depends on system configuration and tensorflow library
7.	KNN Results	Load the dataset and process the KNN Algorithm	Pass	The dataset must be media folder
8.	Predict Train and Test data	Predicted and original salary will be displayed	Pass	Trains and test size must be specify otherwise failed
9.	Admin login	Admin can login with his login credential. If success he get his home page	Pass	Invalid login details will not allowed here
10.	Admin can activate the register users	Admin can activate the register user id	Pass	If user id not found then it won't login.

8. OUTPUTSCREEN

Task 1: open cmd promte to excute code


```
C:\Windows\System32\cmd.exe - python manage.py runserver
Microsoft Windows [Version 10.0.17134.1304]
(c) 2018 Microsoft Corporation. All rights reserved.

C:\Users\Divya\Downloads\abhi pro\Code\StressDetection>python manage.py runserver
Performing system checks...

System check identified no issues (0 silenced).
December 13, 2021 - 15:20:57
Django version 2.0.13, using settings 'StressDetection.settings'
Starting development server at http://127.0.0.1:8000/
Quit the server with CTRL-BREAK.
_
```

Figure 6.2.1: Implementation

Task 2: The User can register the first. While registering he required a valid user email and mobile for further communications.

Stress Detection in IT Professionals Home Users Admin Registrations

User Register Form

User Name	<input type="text"/>
Login ID	<input type="text"/>
Password	<input type="text"/>
Mobile	<input type="text"/>
email	<input type="text"/>
Locality	<input type="text"/>
Address	<input type="text"/>
City	<input type="text"/>
State	<input type="text"/>

Figure 6.2.2: User registration form

Task 3: Admin can login with his credentials. Once he login he can activate the users. The activated user only login in our applications.

Figure 6.2.3 : Activation form

Task 4 : Once admin activated the customer then user can login into our system.

Figure 6.2.4 : User login form

Task 5: First user has to give the input as image to the system the python library will extract the features and appropriate emotion of the image. If given image contain more than one faces also possible to detect.

Upload an Image to test which is 640X480 Resolutions

Select an Image No file chosen

Results table

S.No	User Name	File Name	Emotions	File	Date	Image	Download	Emotions View
1	divya	WhatsApp Image 2021-12-01 at 06.54.54.jpeg	Fear	/media/WhatsApp%20Image%202021-12-01%20at%2006.54.54.jpeg	Dec. 1, 2021, 1:35 p.m.		Download	Emotions View
2	divya	im54.png	Happy	/media/im54.png	Dec. 11, 2021, 4:16 a.m.		Download	Emotions View

Figure 6.2.5 : Uploading Image

Task 6 : The stress level we are going to indicate by facial expression like sad, angry etc.. The image processing completed the we are going to start the live stream. In the live stream also we can get the facial expression more that one persons also.

Figure 6.2.6 : Output Image

9.

CONCLUSION

Stress Detection System is designed to predict stress in the employees by monitoring captured images of authenticated users which makes the system secure. The image capturing is done automatically when the authenticate user is logged in based on some time interval. The captured images are used to detect the stress of the user based on some standard conversion and image processing mechanisms. Then the system will analyze the stress levels by using Machine Learning algorithms which generates the results that are more efficient.

10.

FUTURE ENHANCEMENTS

Biomedical wearable sensors embedded with IOT technology is a proven combination in the health care sector. The benefits of using such devices have positively impacted the patients and doctors alike. Early diagnosis of medical conditions, faster medical assistance by means of Remote Monitoring and Telecommunication, emergency alert mechanism to notify the care taker and personal Doctor, etc are a few of its advantages. The proposed work on developing a multimodal IOT system assures to be a better health assistant for a person by constantly monitoring and providing regular feedback on the stress levels. For future work, it would be interesting to enhance this work into the development of a stress detection model by the addition of other physiological parameters, including an activity recognition system and application of machine learning techniques.

11.

REFERENCES

1. G. Giannakakis, D. Manousos, F. Chiarugi, "Stress and anxiety detection using facial cues from videos," *Biomedical Signal processing and Control*, vol. 31, pp. 89-101, January 2017.
2. T. Jick and R. Payne, "Stress at work," *Journal of Management Education*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 50-56, 1980.
3. Nisha Raichur, Nidhi Lonakadi, Priyanka Mural, "Detection of Stress Using Image Processing and Machine Learning Techniques", vol.9, no. 3S, July 2017.
4. Bhattacharyya, R., & Basu, S. (2018). Retrieved from 'The Economic Times'.
5. OSMI Mental Health in Tech Survey Dataset, 2017
6. U. S. Reddy, A. V. Thota and A. Dharun, "Machine Learning Techniques for Stress Prediction in Working Employees," 2018 IEEE International Conference on Computational Intelligence and Computing Research (ICCIC), Madurai, India, 2018, pp. 1-4.
7. <https://www.kaggle.com/qiriro/stress>
8. Communications, N. . World health report.2001.
9. URL: http://www.who.int/whr/2001/media_centre/press_release/en/.
10. Bakker, J., Holenderski, L., Kocielnik, R., Pechenizkiy, M., Sidorova, N.. *Stess@ work: From measuring stress to its understanding, prediction and handling with personalized coaching*. In: *Proceedings of the 2nd ACM SIGHT International health informatics symposium*. ACM; 2012, p. 673–678.
11. Deng, Y., Wu, Z., Chu, C.H., Zhang, Q., Hsu, D.F.. *Sensor feature selection and combination for stress identification using combinatorial fusion*. *International Journal of Advanced Robotic Systems* 2013;10(8):306.
12. Ghaderi, A., Frounchi, J., Farnam, A.. *Machine learning-based signal processing using physiological signals for stress detection*. In: *2015 22nd Iranian Conference on Biomedical Engineering (ICBME)*. 2015, p. 93–98.
13. Villarejo, M.V., Zapirain, B.G., Zorrilla, A.M.. *A stress sensor based on galvanic skin response (gsr) controlled by zigbee*. *Sensors* 2012; 12(5):6075–6101.
14. Liu, D., Ulrich, M.. *Listen to your heart: Stress prediction using consumer heart rate sensors* 2015;.

15. Nakashima, Y., Kim, J., Flutura, S., Seiderer, A., Andre, E.. Stress recognition in daily work. In: *International Symposium on Pervasive Computing Paradigms for Mental Health*. Springer; 2015, p. 23–33.
16. Xu, Q., Nwe, T.L., Guan, C.. Cluster-based analysis for personalized stress evaluation using physiological signals. *IEEE journal of biomedical and health informatics* 2015;19(1):275
17. Tanev, G., Saadi, D.B., Hoppe, K., Sorensen, H.B.. Classification of acute stress using linear and non-linear heart rate variability analysis derived from sternal ecg. In: *Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC), 2014 36th Annual International Conference of the IEEE*. IEEE; 2014, p. 3386–3389.
18. Gjoreski, M., Gjoreski, H., Lustrek, M., Gams, M.. Continuous stress detection using a wrist device: in laboratory and real life. In: *Proceedings of the 2016 ACM International Joint Conference on Pervasive and Ubiquitous Computing: Adjunct*. ACM; 2016, p. 1185–1193.
19. Palanisamy, K., Murugappan, M., Yaacob, S.. Multiple physiological signal-based human stress identification using non-linear classifiers. *Elektronika ir elektrotechnika* 2013;19(7):80–85.
20. Widanti, N., Sumanto, B., Rosa, P., Miftahudin, M.F.. Stress level detection using heart rate, blood pressure, and gsr and stress therapy by utilizing infrared. In: *Industrial Instrumentation and Control (ICIC), 2015 International Conference on*. IEEE; 2015, p. 275–279.
21. Sioni, R., Chittaro, L.. Stress detection using physiological sensors. *Computer* 2015;48(10):26–33.
22. Zenonos, A., Khan, A., Kalogridis, G., Vatsikas, S., Lewis, T., Sooriyabandara, M.. Healthyoffice: Mood recognition at work using smartphones and wearable sensors. In: *Pervasive Computing and Communication Workshops (PerCom Workshops), 2016 IEEE International Conference on*. IEEE; 2016, p. 1–6.
23. Selvaraj, N.. Psychological acute stress measurement using a wireless adhesive biosensor. In: *2015 37th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC)*. 2015, p. 3137–3140.
24. Vadana, D.P., Kottayil, S.K.. Energy-aware intelligent controller for dynamic energy management on smart microgrid. In: *Power and Energy Systems Conference: Towards Sustainable Energy, 2014*. IEEE; 2014, p. 1–7.

25. Rajagopalan, S.S., Murthy, O.R., Goecke, R., Rozga, A.. Play with mememeasuring a child's engagement in a social interaction. In: Automatic Face and Gesture Recognition (FG), 2015 11th IEEE International Conference and Workshops on; vol. 1. IEEE; 2015, p. 1–8.
26. Koldijk, S., Neerincx, M.A., Kraaij, W.. Detecting work stress in offices by combining unobtrusive sensors. *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing* 2016;.
27. Koldijk, S., Sappelli, M., Verberne, S., Neerincx, M.A., Kraaij, W.. The swell knowledge work dataset for stress and user modeling research. In: Proceedings of the 16th International Conference on Multimodal Interaction; ICMI '14. New York, NY, USA: ACM. ISBN 978-1-4503-2885-2; 2014, p. 291–298. URL: <http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/2663204.2663257>. doi:10.1145/2663204.2663257. Yoder, N.. Peak finder. Internet: <http://www.mathworks.com/matlabcentral/fileexchange/25500> 2011

Author Citations

1. Acharya, Kamal, *Attendance Management System Project* (April 28, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4810251> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4810251>
2. Acharya, Kamal, *Online Food Order System* (May 2, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4814732> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4814732>
3. Acharya, Kamal, *University management system project*. (May 1, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4814103> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4814103>
4. Acharya, Kamal, *Online banking management system*. (May 1, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4813597> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4813597>
5. Acharya, Kamal, *Online Job Portal Management System* (May 5, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4817534> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4817534>
6. Acharya, Kamal, *Employee leave management system*. (May 7, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4819626> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4819626>
7. Acharya, Kamal, *Online electricity billing project report*. (May 7, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4819630> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4819630>
8. Acharya, Kamal, *POLICY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. (December 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831694> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831694>
9. Acharya, Kamal, *Online job placement system project report*. (January 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831638> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831638>
10. Acharya, Kamal, *Software testing for project report*. (May 16, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831028> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831028>
11. Acharya, Kamal, *ONLINE CRIME REPORTING SYSTEM PROJECT*. (August 10, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831015> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831015>
12. Acharya, Kamal, *Burger ordering system project report*. (October 10, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4832704> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4832704>
13. Acharya, Kamal, *Teachers Record Management System Project Report* (December 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4833821> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4833821>
14. Acharya, Kamal, *Dairy Management System Project Report* (December 20, 2020). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835231> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835231>
15. Acharya, Kamal, *Electrical Shop Management System Project* (December 10, 2019). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835238> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835238>
16. Acharya, Kamal, *Online book store management system project report*. (February 10, 2020). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835277> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835277>

17. Acharya, Kamal, *Paint shop management system project report*. (January 10, 2019). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835441> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835441>
18. Acharya, Kamal, *Supermarket billing system project report*. (August 10, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835474> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835474>
19. Acharya, Kamal, *Online taxi booking system project report*. (March 10, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4837729> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4837729>
20. Acharya, Kamal, *Online car servicing system project report*. (March 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4837832> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4837832>
21. Acharya, Kamal, *School management system project report*. (July 10, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4837837> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4837837>
22. Acharya, Kamal, *Furniture Showroom Management System Project Report* (March 21, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4839422> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4839422>
23. Acharya, Kamal, *Online Vehicle Rental System Project Report* (March 21, 2019). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4839429> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4839429>
24. Acharya, Kamal, *Fruit Shop Management System Project Report* (August 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841048> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841048>
25. Acharya, Kamal, *Hall Booking Management System Project Report* (December 21, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841055> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841055>
26. Acharya, Kamal, *Lundry Management System Project Report* (October 21, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841059> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841059>
27. Acharya, Kamal, *A CASE STUDY OF CINEMA MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT* (September 25, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841209> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841209>
28. Acharya, Kamal, *A CASE STUDY ON ONLINE TICKET BOOKING SYSTEM PROJECT* (May 25, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841210> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841210>
29. Acharya, Kamal, *ONLINE DATING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. (April 25, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842066> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842066>
30. Acharya, Kamal, *ONLINE RESUME BUILDER MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. (April 25, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842071> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842071>
31. Acharya, Kamal, *TOLL TEX MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT* (August 21, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842082> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842082>
32. Acharya, Kamal, *Chat Application Through Client Server Management System Project Report* (June 25, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842761> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842761>

33. Acharya, Kamal, *Web Chatting Application Management System Project Report* (April 25,2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842771> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842771>
34. Acharya, Kamal, *Automobile management system project report* (May 25, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4846917> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4846917>
35. Acharya, Kamal, *College bus management system project report* (April 25, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4846920> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4846920>
36. Acharya, Kamal, *Courier management system project report* (May 25, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4846922> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4846922>
37. Acharya, Kamal, *Event management system project report* (April 25, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4846927> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4846927>
38. Acharya, Kamal, *Library management system project report II* (May 25, 2020). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4848857> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4848857>
39. Kamal Acharya. *Teacher record management system project report*. Authorea. August 02, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172261514.46787329/v1>
40. Kamal Acharya. *POST OFFICE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. Authorea. August 02, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172261514.44494375/v1>
41. Kamal Acharya. *Fruit shop management system project report*. Authorea. August 02, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172261514.42227675/v1>
42. Kamal Acharya. *Dairy management system project report*. Authorea. August 02, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172261513.39402347/v1>
43. Kamal Acharya. *DATA COMMUNICATION AND COMPUTER NETWORKMANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254873.37480177/v1>
44. Kamal Acharya. *School management system project report*. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254873.34023165/v1>
45. Kamal Acharya. *A CASE STUDY OF CINEMA MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT*. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254873.30191075/v1>
46. Kamal Acharya. *A CASE STUDY ON ONLINE TICKET BOOKING SYSTEM PROJECT*. Authorea. August 01, 2024 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254872.26972790/v1>
47. Kamal Acharya. *Web chatting application project report managementsystem*. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254871.18588592/v1>
48. Kamal Acharya. *RETAIL STORE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254871.14590154/v1>

49. Kamal Acharya. *SUPERMARKET MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172252491.19145062/v1>
50. Kamal Acharya. *SOCIAL MEDIA MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172252491.11210579/v1>
51. Kamal Acharya. *Online music portal management system project report*. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172252488.89734698/v1>
52. Kamal Acharya. *COLLEGE BUS MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. Authorea. July 31, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172245277.70798942/v1>
53. Kamal Acharya. *AUTOMOBILE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. Authorea. July 31, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172245276.67982593/v1>
54. Kamal Acharya. *Ludo management system project report*. Authorea. July 31, 2024 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172243999.98091616/v1>
55. Kamal Acharya. *Literature online quiz system project report*. Authorea. July 31, 2024 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172243825.53562953/v1>
56. Kamal Acharya. *Avoid waste management system project*. Authorea. July 29, 2024 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172228528.85022205/v1>
57. Kamal Acharya. *CHAT APPLICATION THROUGH CLIENT SERVER MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT*. Authorea. July 29, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172228527.74316529/v1>
58. Kamal Acharya. *Parking allotment system project report*. Authorea. July 29, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172227078.89966943/v1>
59. Kamal Acharya. *HEALTH INSURANCE CLAIM MANAGEMENT SYSTEM*. Authorea. July 26, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172202020.06707762/v1>
60. Kamal Acharya. *ONLINE TRAIN BOOKING SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. Authorea. July 22, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172167914.45160406/v1>
61. Kamal Acharya. *COVID MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. Authorea. July 16, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172116616.60220024/v1>
62. Kamal Acharya. *Web development system project report*. Authorea. November 12, 2024. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.173144769.91595244/v1>.
63. Kamal Acharya. *Tourism management system project report*. Authorea. November 12, 2024. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.173144144.44637261/v1>
64. Kamal Acharya. *Wireless charging in mobile phone management system project report*. Authorea. November 08, 2024. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.173109197.71419168/v1>

65. Kamal Acharya. *Human Age and Gender Prediction Management system project report*. Authorea. November 07, 2024. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.173101380.07915161/v1>
66. Kamal Acharya. *Computer graphics management system project report*. Authorea. November 06, 2024. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.173092081.18568024/v1>
67. .Kamal Acharya. *Advanced hospital management system project report*. Authorea. November 05, 2024. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.173083558.80262227/v1>
68. Kamal Acharya. *Library management system project report II*. Authorea. October 31, 2024. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.173040872.26706796/v1>
69. Kamal Acharya. *Student Information Management System Project Report II*. Authorea. October 31, 2024. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.173040871.12765931/v1>
70. Kamal Acharya. *online musical instrumental store management system project report*. Authorea. October 31, 2024. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.173040863.37700877/v1>
71. Kamal Acharya. *Leave management system project report*. Authorea. October 29, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.173023610.07320124/v1>
72. Kamal Acharya. *Resort Management and Reservation System Project Report*. Authorea. October 29, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.173016279.97900083/v1>
73. Kamal Acharya. *How Google Search Works*. Authorea. October 22, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172961967.70431246/v1>
74. Kamal Acharya. *A case study of social media and its perceived effects to student in academic performance*. Authorea. October 21, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172953990.07689253/v1>
75. Kamal Acharya. *Integration of Sensor Network to Internet of Things (IoT) for Application of Smart Home using Open Source Computing*. Authorea. October 17, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172918899.98182290/v1>
76. Kamal Acharya. *Case studies of common csharp project report*. Authorea. October 16, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172910505.57176321/v1>
77. Kamal Acharya. *Computerized enrollment system project report*. Authorea. October 14, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172893928.82416786/v1>
78. Kamal Acharya. *Clothes management system project report*. Authorea. November 15, 2024. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.173169338.85270304/v1>
79. Kamal Acharya. *Company visitor management system projec report*. Authorea. November 15, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.173169336.67380865/v1>
80. Kamal Acharya. *Training and placement cell management system*. Authorea. November 14, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.173161607.73300668/v1>

81. Kamal Acharya. *Virtual Mouse using Hand Gestures*. Authorea. November 14, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.173161606.61659157/v1>
82. Kamal Acharya. *COMPUTER INSTITUTE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT* . Authorea. March 13, 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.174189026.67281599/v1>
83. Kamal Acharya. *Online directory management system project*. Authorea. June 11, 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.174965566.61058065/v1>
84. Acharya, Kamal, *Automatic Pronunciation Mistake Detector* (June 10, 2025). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=5290038> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5290038>
85. Acharya, Kamal, *Book Store Management System Project* (June 02, 2025). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=5290050> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5290050>
86. Acharya, Kamal, *E-Helping Housing Society Project Report* (June 02, 2025). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=5290052> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5290052>
87. Acharya, Kamal, *Online Directory Management System Project* (June 07, 2025). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=5284995> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5284995>
88. Acharya, Kamal, *Hotel Billing Management System Project Report* (May 07, 2025). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=5284997> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5284997>